

QUIZ

LAST NAME: AIST

FIRST NAME: JENNIFER

PROGRAM CODE: MIPH

COURSE CODE : ACA-401

PERIOD NUMBER: 6

INSTRUCTOR: GULMA

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.
The author used Turabian (footnotes)
The author did use Zotero to insert references
The author used the following software: MS Word 2016 on Mac OS 10.15.3

QUIZ: A SUMMATIVE ASSESSMENT

1. ***The WHO style guide calls to avoid sex stereotyping, patronizing or demeaning expressions in publications. Which one of the following statements meets these requirements?***
 - The patient works full-time in the automotive industry.¹**
 - The patient works full-time as the first female mechanic in the automotive industry.
 - The female patient was allowed to work full-time in the automotive industry.
 - The patient's husband permits her to work full-time because he is out of work.

2. ***A Manual for Writers describes three different types of questions researchers should ask. Which of the following are those questions?***

¹ World Health Organization. *WHO Style Guide* (Malta: World Health Organization, 2004), 56.

- The three types of questions are conceptual, practical and applied.**²
- The three types of questions are contrived, practical and applied.
- The three types of questions are hypothetical, ethical and profound.
- The three types of questions are factual, interpretive and evaluative.
3. **Which of the following is NOT recommended in regard to sources?**
- Consult primary sources for evidence.
- Read quaternary sources to obtain the most current evidence.**³
- Read tertiary sources for introductory overviews.
- Read secondary sources to learn from other researchers.
4. **Which of the following is NOT a problem with failing to proofread?**
- Submitting work with incomplete sentences.
- Submitting work with redundant phrases.
- Submitting work which flows well and is free of errors.**⁴
- Submitting work with numerous misspellings.
5. **In regard to punctuation, which one is considered to be the most important?**

² Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations, Eighth Edition: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, ed. Wayne C. Booth et al., Eighth edition (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2013), 16-17.

³ Kate L. Turabian, 24-25.

⁴ EUCLID, *ACA-401 Coursepack. Period 1* (2nd ed. Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University, 2019), 6.

- The semi colon is the most important.
- The comma is the most important.⁵**
- The full stop or period is the most important.
- Quotation marks are the most important.

6. **Which of the following best describes the purpose of a style guide?**

- Style guides are templates within word processing software to aid writers in layout design.
- Style guides are strict rules all writers must abide by in regard to aspects of writing such as manuscript layout, font, spelling and accepted terminology to name a few.
- Style guides vary amongst different organizations.
- Style guides provide a means for writers to produce consistent pieces of work in regard to aspects such as manuscript layout, font, spelling, and accepted terminology to name a few.⁶**

7. **Which of the following statements best describes the purpose of experimental science?**

- The purpose of experimental science is to discover the truth—not to make the data conform to one’s expectations.⁷**
- The purpose of experimental science is to discover the truth—your data should always match your hypothesis.

⁵ Patrick Sebranek, Dave Kemper, and Verne Meyer, *WriteSource 2000* (Massachusetts: Great Source Education Group, 1999), 389.

⁶ EUCLID, 24-25.

⁷ EUCLID, *ACA-401 Coursepack Period 4* (Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University, 2020), 11.

- The purpose of experimental science is to ask questions that will match your findings.
 - The purpose of experimental science is to advance your position in your organization.
8. **Which of the following is NOT a reason to provide citations and references?**
- To demonstrate that you have gathered evidence to support your ideas and arguments.
 - To demonstrate that you have used credible sources.
 - To demonstrate that you have read widely and at the appropriate academic level.
 - To demonstrate your proficiency in using citation software such as Zotero.⁸**
9. **Writers often paraphrase as a means to share the ideas of an author in your own words. Which of the following is NOT a key point to ensure the paraphrase looks different than how the author originally wrote it?**
- Any paraphrase must be properly cited.
 - The paraphrase must include a couple of your own words to make it a little bit different from what the author wrote.⁹**
 - The paraphrase must accurately represent what the author wrote.
 - The writing style you use must be different from the original author.

⁸ EUCLID, 55.

⁹ EUCLID, 8.

10. Staying focused is critical to the writing process. Which of the following is an example of why?

- Failing to focus on a topic can result in distraction and is not likely to be done well.¹⁰
- Turning off background music or the television will help writers focus on their work.
- Writers who experience Attention Deficit Hyperactivity Disorder have a difficult time focusing on writing assignments.
- Choosing very broad topics will help writers to focus.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

Cleenewerck, Laurent, and Kabiru Gulma. *ACA-401 Coursepack: Period 1*. 2nd ed. Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University, 2019.

Cleenewerck, Laurent, and Kabiru Gulma. *ACA-401 Coursepack: Period 4*. Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University, 2020.

Sebranek, Patrick, Dave Kemper, and Verne Meyer. *WriteSource 2000*. Massachusetts: Great Source Education Group, 1999.

Turabian, Kate L. *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations, Eighth Edition: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*. Edited by Wayne C. Booth, Gregory G. Colomb, Joseph M. Williams, and University of Chicago Press Staff. Eighth edition. Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2013.

World Health Organization. *WHO Style Guide*. Malta: World Health Organization, 2004.

¹⁰ EUCLID, 14.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.